

Oral Presentation #19 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Infantile hemangiomas (IHs) are common benign vascular tumors of infancy that typically follow a self-limiting course. However, treatment may be required when lesion size, location, or associated complications pose functional or cosmetic concerns. Propranolol, a non-selective beta-blocker, has emerged as the first-line therapy for complicated IHs due to its high efficacy and favorable safety profile.

Case Presentation: This case report describes a 5-month-old female infant presenting with a scalp-localized hemangioma successfully managed with oral propranolol.

Discussion: Following the initiation of treatment and close cardiovascular monitoring, a significant reduction in lesion size and discoloration was observed, with no adverse events reported. This case underscores the importance of early diagnosis, individualized treatment planning, and multidisciplinary follow-up in the management of IHs.

Conclusion: Our findings contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting propranolol as an effective and safe therapeutic option for infantile hemangiomas.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Infantile hemangioma, propranolol

INTRODUCTION

Infantile hemangioma (IH) is the most common benign vascular tumor of infancy, typically appearing shortly after birth or within the first few weeks of life. Epidemiological studies report that the incidence of visible lesions at birth is approximately 4–5%, increasing up to 20% in premature infants (Leung, Lam, Leong, & Hon, 2021). Clinically, typical IHs exhibit a rapid proliferation phase, followed by gradual regression during the involution stage. This natural course typically spans several years; however, residual sequelae may persist in some cases (Jung, 2021).

Female sex, prematurity, low birth weight, twin pregnancies, and Caucasian ethnicity are recognized risk factors for the development of IH (Krowchuk et al., 2019). IHs are most commonly localized to the head and neck region, where they may cause both aesthetic and functional complications. Lesions situated in the periorbital, perinasal, perioral, or anogenital areas, or those associated with ulceration, bleeding, infection, or risk of airway obstruction, may necessitate medical intervention (Drolet, Swanson, & Frieden, 2013).

In 2008, Léauté-Labrèze and colleagues demonstrated the efficacy of oral propranolol in the treatment of IH, leading to its establishment as the first-line systemic therapy. Propranolol inhibits lesion growth and accelerates regression through mechanisms such as vasoconstriction, suppression of cellular proliferation, and inhibition of angiogenesis (Léauté-Labrèze et al., 2015). This case report presents the successful management of a scalp-localized infantile hemangioma with propranolol therapy.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 5-month-old female infant presented with redness and swelling on the scalp, first noticed shortly after birth. The family history was unremarkable for similar vascular conditions or systemic illnesses. Physical examination revealed a raised, irregularly bordered, red-pink infantile hemangioma measuring approximately 2×3 cm in the right parietal region (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Initial clinical appearance of the scalp-localized infantile hemangioma in a 5-month-old female infant prior to propranolol treatment.

Laboratory investigations were within normal limits. Transfontanel and abdominal ultrasonography findings were unremarkable. Before initiating treatment, the patient was referred to pediatric cardiology, and both electrocardiography and echocardiography results were normal.

Oral propranolol therapy was initiated at a starting dose of 0.5 mg/kg/day. The patient was monitored for 24 hours for potential cardiovascular adverse effects. Vital signs remained stable during the observation period, and the dose was gradually increased to 2 mg/kg/day. In the following weeks, significant regression in lesion dimensions and fading of coloration were observed (Figure 2). Propranolol therapy was continued for 12 months, with no serious adverse events recorded throughout the treatment course.

Figure 2

Marked regression and discoloration of the lesion after 12 months of oral propranolol therapy. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient.

DISCUSSION

Although most infantile hemangiomas follow a benign and self-limiting course, certain lesions may cause functional or life-threatening complications beyond cosmetic concerns. Current clinical guidelines recommend that treatment decisions be based on lesion size, location, complication potential, and growth dynamics (Krowchuk et al., 2019).

Oral propranolol has become the first-line systemic treatment for IH. Its efficacy was initially reported in 2008 and has since been confirmed through multicenter studies (Hogeling, Adams, & Wargon, 2011; Léauté-Labrèze et al., 2015). Propranolol typically elicits a rapid clinical response, marked by a reduction in lesion size and fading of coloration. Its mechanism of action is multifactorial, beginning with vasoconstriction and followed by the suppression of angiogenic factors such as VEGF and bFGF, thereby accelerating hemangioma involution (Cohen, Friedman, & Drolet, 2017). However, careful patient selection and close monitoring are essential due to the potential side effects, including hypoglycemia, bradycardia, hypotension, and bronchospasm (Baumann, Metzler, & Schmid, 2016). In our case, a prompt and favorable response to propranolol was observed, with a notable reduction in lesion size and color intensity. No systemic adverse events were encountered, and the treatment was well tolerated. Dose titration was performed as needed, and clinical response was monitored throughout the treatment, consistent with current practice guidelines. The duration of therapy typically ranges from 6 to 12 months but may be extended up to 18 months in selected cases (Jung, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Although infantile hemangiomas are generally benign, some cases may pose significant risks depending on the lesion's location and growth behavior. Propranolol is a safe and effective agent in managing these lesions, achieving high success rates through appropriate patient selection and careful monitoring. This case adds to the growing body of evidence supporting the efficacy and safety of propranolol in the treatment of IH. A multidisciplinary approach and individualized patient assessment are essential throughout the management process.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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